

ANALYSIS OF INTERFACE FRACTURE IN LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with the theory and methodology for predicting delamination in composites. Constituent materials in the composites are considered to be homogeneous and elastic, but can be isotropic, orthotropic or completely anisotropic. The crack tip displacement field will be determined based on the theory proposed by Rice¹ and Suo². The energy release rate is computed by the method of virtual crack extension of Parks³. A computational method for stress intensity factors follows the technique by Matos *et al.*⁴. The methodology are demonstrated by a computer program for problems of delamination in composites under arbitrary geometrical and loading conditions.

Keywords: Delamination in composites, interface crack, anisotropic materials.

INTRODUCTION

Delamination in composites is one of major sources of failure of composites. To prevent these types of failure, we need to study the strength of composites. One approach is the investigation of the initiation and growth of interface cracks between two dissimilar materials and their interactions with local failure of composites. The advantage of this approach is that it can provide us with not only information on the critical load for interface fracture initiation but also the time span required for interface crack propagation prior to catastrophic failure. In addition, this approach can also predict branching of the interface crack propagation. The objective of this research is to establish a finite element method for the investigation of stress intensity factors and energy release rate for an interface crack between two dissimilar elastic materials (Fig. 1) which can be isotropic, orthotropic or completely anisotropic. In this study, we shall employ a crack tip displacement field based on the work done by Rice¹ and Suo² on singularities near the tip of the interface crack respectively for isotropic and anisotropic bimaterials. The J -integral will be calculated in accordance with the energy release rate³. Problems caused by stress singularities and oscillations can be avoided through the J -integral approach. Stress intensity factors will then be determined based on the rate of increase in the value of the J -integral due to the superposition of a special crack tip displacement field as suggested by Matos, McMeeking, Charalambides and Drory⁴ in their work on interface crack between two isotropic materials.

In problems of interface crack between two dissimilar materials, complexities are induced by oscillations in stresses and crack opening displacements. Thus any stress intensity factors calculated by the crack tip element method would be sensitive to the size of the crack tip region used in the finite element computation. Although the oscillation behavior can be eliminated if

Figure 1. Geometry of the problem.

Figure 2. A four-point-bending beam.

either plasticity⁵ or interface contact stress⁶ are considered in its analysis, these inclusions however can produce additional complications in computation. In this work, we shall determine the complex stress intensity factor through an elastic analysis. We shall use the complex stress intensity factor to predict the interface fracture propagation.

ASYMPTOTIC FIELDS NEAR THE CRACK TIP

A general study of crack tip fields of an interface crack between two semi-infinite anisotropic elastic media has been done by Suo². His theory can be summarized as follows.

Consider two anisotropic elastic media bounded by a straight interface as shown in Fig. 1. Define strain and stress matrices by

$$\{\epsilon_i\} = \{\epsilon_{11} \ \epsilon_{22} \ \epsilon_{33} \ 2\epsilon_{23} \ 2\epsilon_{31} \ 2\epsilon_{12}\}^T, \quad \{\sigma_i\} = \{\sigma_{11} \ \sigma_{22} \ \sigma_{33} \ \sigma_{23} \ \sigma_{31} \ \sigma_{12}\}^T. \quad (1)$$

We shall consider two-dimensional problems where geometry and loading conditions are independent of x_3 . Let s_{ij} be the elastic compliance coefficients such that

$$\epsilon_i = \sum_{j=1}^6 s_{ij} \sigma_j, \quad (2)$$

It has been shown by Lekhnitskii¹⁰ and Eshelby *et al.*¹¹ that for a two dimensional problem, the elastic field can be represented in terms of three functions $f_1(z_1), f_2(z_2), f_3(z_3)$. Each of them is holomorphic in its argument $z_j = x + \mu_j y$, where μ_j are three distinct complex numbers with positive imaginary part. The complex numbers can be solved as roots of a sixtic polynomial which will be given later. With these holomorphic functions, the displacement u_i and stresses σ_{ij} can be represented by

$$u_i = 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{j=1}^3 A_{ij} f_j(z_j) \right], \quad \sigma_{2i} = 2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{j=1}^3 L_{ij} f_j'(z_j) \right], \quad \sigma_{1i} = -2 \operatorname{Re} \left[\sum_{j=1}^3 L_{ij} \mu_j f_j'(z_j) \right] \quad (3)$$

for $i = 1, 2, 3$, where A and L are two 3×3 matrices whose elements depend on the elastic constants.

On the bases of two Airy-type stress functions, Lekhnitskii¹⁰ found that μ_α ($\alpha=1, \dots, 6$) satisfies the following sixtic characteristic equation

$$l_2(\mu)l_4(\mu) - [l_3(\mu)]^2 = 0, \quad (4)$$

where

$$l_2(\mu) = s_{55}\mu^2 - 2s_{45}\mu + s_{44}, \quad l_3(\mu) = s_{15}\mu^3 - (s_{14}+s_{56})\mu^2 + (s_{25}+s_{46})\mu - s_{24},$$

$$l_4(\mu) = s_{11}\mu^4 - 2s_{16}\mu^3 + (2s_{12}+s_{66})\mu^2 - 2s_{26}\mu + s_{22}. \quad (5)$$

We choose three roots μ_j with positive imaginary part, μ_1, μ_2 and μ_3 . For the case of plane stress deformation, we calculate the following matrix for both materials

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} -\mu_1 & -\mu_2 & -\mu_3\eta_3 \\ 1 & 1 & \eta_3 \\ -\eta_1 & -\eta_2 & -1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\eta_i = -l_3(\mu_i)/l_2(\mu_i) \quad \text{for } i=1,2, \quad \eta_3 = -l_3(\mu_3)/l_4(\mu_3). \quad (7)$$

Then we evaluate A_{ij} for $i,j = 1,2,3$ according to

$$A_{1j} = s_{11}\mu_j^2 + s_{12} - s_{16}\mu_j + \eta_j(s_{15}\mu_j - s_{14}), \quad A_{2j} = s_{21}\mu_j + \frac{s_{22}}{\mu_j} - s_{26} + \eta_j\left(s_{25} - \frac{s_{24}}{\mu_j}\right),$$

$$A_{3j} = s_{41}\mu_j + \frac{s_{42}}{\mu_j} - s_{46} + \eta_j\left(s_{45} - \frac{s_{44}}{\mu_j}\right) \quad (8)$$

for $j = 1,2$, and

$$A_{13} = \eta_3\left(s_{11}\mu_3^2 + s_{12} - \frac{s_{16}}{\mu_3}\right) + s_{15}\mu_3 - s_{14}, \quad A_{23} = \eta_3\left(s_{21}\mu_3 + \frac{s_{22}}{\mu_3} - s_{26}\right) + s_{25} - \frac{s_{24}}{\mu_3},$$

$$A_{33} = \eta_3\left(s_{41}\mu_3 + \frac{s_{42}}{\mu_3} - s_{46}\right) + s_{45} - \frac{s_{44}}{\mu_3}. \quad (9)$$

For the case of plane strain deformation, we replace s_{ij} in equations (8) and (9) by

$$s'_{ij} = s_{ij} - \frac{s_{i3}s_{j3}}{s_{33}} \quad \text{for } i,j = 1,2,3. \quad (10)$$

In both cases of plane stress and plane strain, we then evaluate

$$B = iAL^{-1}, \quad H = B_1 + \bar{B}_2 \quad (11)$$

where $A = \{A_{ij}\}$ and B_1 and B_2 refer to material 1 and material 2 respectively. The super bar represents the complex conjugate of the corresponding quantity. Next, we solve the eigenvalue problem

$$\bar{H}w = e^{2\pi\epsilon}Hw, \quad (12)$$

where ϵ is the eigenvalue and w is the corresponding eigenfunction. In the solution, we choose

$$\mathbf{w} = [-i/2, *, *]^T, \quad \mathbf{w}_3 = [*, *, 1]^T, \quad (13)$$

where * signifies numbers determined by the eigenvalue problem. Denote $z = x + \mu y$. Let $K = K_I + iK_{II}$ be the complex in-plane stress intensity factor and K_{III} be the anti-plane stress intensity factor. It is obtained by Suo [2] that

$$f_1'(z) = \frac{1}{2(2\pi z)^{1/2} \cosh \pi \varepsilon} (e^{\pi \varepsilon K z i \varepsilon L_1^{-1} \mathbf{w}} + e^{-\pi \varepsilon \bar{K} z^{-i \varepsilon L_1^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{w}}}) + \frac{1}{(2\pi z)^{1/2}} K_{III} L_1^{-1} \mathbf{w}_3, \quad (14)$$

and

$$f_1(z) = \frac{1}{2 \cosh \pi \varepsilon} \left(\frac{z}{2\pi} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{2}{1+2i\varepsilon} e^{\pi \varepsilon K z i \varepsilon L_1^{-1} \mathbf{w}} + \frac{2}{1-2i\varepsilon} e^{-\pi \varepsilon \bar{K} z^{-i \varepsilon L_1^{-1} \bar{\mathbf{w}}}) \right) + K_{III} \left(\frac{z}{2\pi} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} L_1^{-1} \mathbf{w}_3, \quad (15)$$

$f_2'(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ can be derived from $f_1'(z)$ and $f_1(z)$ by interchanging $e^{\pi \varepsilon}$ with $e^{-\pi \varepsilon}$ and replacing L_1^{-1} by L_2^{-1} . The subscripts 1 and 2 denote respectively material 1 and material 2. Since there are three roots of μ with positive imaginary parts μ_1, μ_2, μ_3 , we can define three complex quantities $z_j = x + \mu_j y$ for $j = 1, 2, 3$ and three complex functions $f_j = f_j(z_j)$, where the origin $x = 0, y = 0$ is set at the tip of the crack. The asymptotic displacement and stress fields can be determined by equation (4). They can be expressed in matrix type by

$$\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2, u_3]^T = 2 \operatorname{Re} [A f(z)], \quad \sigma_2 = [\sigma_{21}, \sigma_{22}, \sigma_{23}]^T = 2 \operatorname{Re} [L f'(z)], \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_1 = [\sigma_{11}, \sigma_{12}, \sigma_{13}]^T = -2 \operatorname{Re} [M f'(z)]. \quad (17)$$

In equation (17), matrix M is a diagonal matrix with μ_1, μ_2 and μ_3 as its main diagonal elements.

The J -integral (or the energy release rate) can be expressed by

$$J = \frac{\bar{\mathbf{w}}^T (\mathbf{H} + \bar{\mathbf{H}}) \mathbf{w}}{4 \cosh^2 \pi \varepsilon} (K_I^2 + K_{II}^2) + \frac{1}{8} \mathbf{w}_3^T (\mathbf{H} + \bar{\mathbf{H}}) \mathbf{w}_3 K_{III}^2 \quad (18)$$

DETERMINATION OF STRESS INTENSITY FACTORS

According to Parks virtual crack extension method³ for a traction free crack, the J -integral (or energy release rate) can be determined by

$$J = - \frac{\partial U}{\partial a} \Big|_F = - \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{u}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{S}}{\partial a} \mathbf{u}, \quad (19)$$

where U is the potential energy of the medium and the differentiation with respect to crack length a is carried out at a fixed load. The vector \mathbf{u} contains elements of the nodal displacements from finite element calculation. \mathbf{S} is the stiffness matrix for the mesh of problem used to solve the crack problem. In the virtual crack extension method, the crack problem is solved first to obtain the vector \mathbf{u} . Then a small virtual crack extension is imposed in the plane of the crack and a new value of the stiffness matrix is computed. The crack is extended by rigidly moving a core of elements around the crack tip. Elements in an annular region are distorted, all elements outside the distorted ring are held

rigid. Consequently in the rigid core and in the outer rigid area, $\frac{\partial S}{\partial u} = 0$. As a result, the computation of J in equation (19) involves a multiplication of a small matrix by two small vectors for the distorted annular region. This method has been used extensively to compute single mode stress intensity factors in the case of single material.

Next we choose small increments of $\Delta K_I, \Delta K_{II}, \Delta K_{III}$ to the stress intensity factors K_I, K_{II}, K_{III} respectively. Correspondingly, $\Delta K_I, \Delta K_{II}, \Delta K_{III}$ will generate respectively small increments of asymptotic displacement fields $\Delta u_I, \Delta u_{II}, \Delta u_{III}$ according to the equations (15) and (16). Thus, the increments of J -integrals $\Delta J_I, \Delta J_{II}, \Delta J_{III}$ can be calculated. Denote the increment of J due to the increment ΔK_i of K_i by $\Delta_j J$ for $i = I, II, III$. The stress intensity factors can be found from equation (18) as

$$K_I = \frac{1}{2C} \frac{\Delta_j J}{\Delta K_I} - \frac{\Delta K_I}{2}, \quad K_{II} = \frac{1}{2C} \frac{\Delta_{II} J}{\Delta K_{II}} - \frac{\Delta K_{II}}{2}, \quad K_{III} = \frac{1}{2C'} \frac{\Delta_{III} J}{\Delta K_{III}} - \frac{\Delta K_{III}}{2}, \quad (20)$$

More explanation regarding the increases in the J -integrals, $\Delta_j J, \Delta_{II} J$ and $\Delta_{III} J$ are needed. Let us solve for u by means of the finite element method, then compute J by the virtual crack extension technique using equation (19). Then we add the displacement Δu_I to u for a problem in the same geometry for which $K_{II} = 0, K_{III} = 0$ and $K_I = \Delta K_I$ which is a small number. It should be noted that the increments of nodal displacement Δu_I is needed only for the nodes associated with the distorted elements in the annular region. Consequently, the asymptotic crack tip displacements thus obtained can be used as the suitable field. With the value of $\frac{\partial S}{\partial u}$ already computed for the first computation of J , the calculation in equation (19) is repeated with the vector $u + \Delta u_I$ used instead of u alone. The value of $J + \Delta_j J$ can then be obtained. The same procedure can be repeated for the incremental vector Δu_{II} with $K_I = 0, K_{III} = 0$ and $K_{II} = \Delta K_{II}$ to obtain $J + \Delta_{II} J$. Finally, from the incremental vector Δu_{III} with $K_I = 0, K_{II} = 0$ and $K_{III} = \Delta K_{III}$, we are able to obtain $J + \Delta_{III} J$.

CRITERIA FOR INTERFACIAL FRACTURE

The use of composite materials in structural design requires the assurance of safety and efficiency. The design process must involve the comparison of the state of stress and deformation with allowable values for the composite materials. It is found that most interface fracture problems involves combinations of normal and shear displacements along the crack. Therefore, mixed mode conditions prevail. Criteria of fracture are employed to predict two phenomena: (1) the stress and/or strain level at the crack onset and (2) the direction of the crack growth. In homogeneous, isotropic brittle materials, cracks tend to grow under mode I condition. A criterion of $K_I = K_{IC}$ is used to assess the stress and/or strain level at the crack onset, and the crack grows along its extension line. If material failures under a mixed mode, a mixed parameter in combination of K_I and K_{II} is employed. In this study, some types of criteria for predicting the direction of crack growth are used such as theories of maximum tangential stress $\sigma_\theta(\theta)$, maximum tangential strain $\epsilon_\theta(\theta)$, maximum energy release rate etc.

METHOD OF COMPUTATION

Our computer program employs the finite element method to solve problems of interfacial cracks between two dissimilar materials in the cases of plane stress, plane strain and anti-plane shearing. The two materials are homogeneous and elastic. But they can be generally anisotropic, orthotropic or isotropic. The aim of the program is to find the energy release rate and the stress intensity factors of the bimaterial. In the computation, four-noded isoparametric elements are used in the entire domain

excluding the vicinity of the crack tip, where singular elements presented by Rice and Tracey¹¹ are adopted for the computation of displacement components.

After finite element meshing, the program computes elemental stiffness matrices and assembles them into a global stiffness matrix. Then, it forms the column of the nodal forces on the right hand side of the finite element equations. It also deals with the boundary conditions on S_u and S_σ and solves the finite element equations for the nodal displacements. Later, the program uses the nodal displacements to obtain the strains and stresses in the elements. Then, the program calculates the energy release rate J , the stress intensity factors K_I , K_{II} and K_{III} and the phase angle $\psi = \tan^{-1}(K_{II}/K_I)$. Finally, the amplitudes of the maximum tangential stress $f(\theta)$ and the amplitudes of the maximum tangential strain $g(\theta)$ near the crack tip are computed for the problem of isotropic bimetals. The quantities $f(\theta)$ and $g(\theta)$ can be used to check the fracture criteria for crack branching for the case of isotropic bimetals.

AN EXAMPLE PROBLEM

Let us consider a four-point-bending beam as the example (Fig. 2). Due to symmetry, only half of the beam needs to be investigated. The beam is subjected to in-plane and anti-plane loads. At the support of the beam, the displacement components in the x_2 and x_3 -directions are constrained. On the axis of symmetry (excluding the open edge), the displacement components in the x_1 -direction are constrained. The sizes of the defined domain of the example and its finite element layout is shown in Fig. 3. There are totally 640 elements and 689 nodes. Each node has three degrees of freedom for the three displacements u_1 , u_2 and u_3 . Three types of bimetals are considered in the example: (1) two isotropic materials, (2) two orthotropic materials and (3) two generally anisotropic materials. Case (1) is treated as an test problem. Its results are compared with those of Matos *et al.*⁴ in the next section.

Figure 3. Finite Element Layout of the four-point bending beam.

Figure 4. Distributions of the amplitudes of the tangential stress $f(\theta)/|K|$ and the tangential strain $g(\theta)/|K|$.

The physical constants of the example problem are given as follows:

Case (1), isotropic bimaterial

In material 1, $E=1.0$, $\nu=0.3$. In material 2, $E=10.0$, $\nu=0.3$;

Case (2), orthotropic bimaterial

In material 1, $E_{11}=1.0$, $E_{22}=0.5$, $E_{33}=0.5$, $\nu_{23}=0.3$, $\nu_{13}=0.3$, $\nu_{12}=0.3$.

In material 2, $E_{11}=10.0$, $E_{22}=5.0$, $E_{33}=5.0$, $\nu_{23}=0.3$, $\nu_{13}=0.3$, $\nu_{12}=0.3$;

Case (3), generally anisotropic bimaterial

For material 1 and material 2, the elastic compliance coefficients are respectively

$$s_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.955 & -0.39 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 \\ -0.39 & 1.82 & 0 & 0 & 0.01 \\ 0 & 0 & 5.2 & 0.1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.1 & 2.6 & 0 \\ 0.01 & 0.01 & 0 & 0 & 2.6 \end{bmatrix}, \quad s_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.0955 & -0.039 & 0 & 0 & 0.001 \\ -0.039 & 0.182 & 0 & 0 & 0.001 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.52 & 0.01 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.01 & 0.26 & 0 \\ 0.001 & 0.001 & 0 & 0 & 0.26 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Some output data are summarized in Table 1. The dimensionless stress intensity factors \hat{K}_I , \hat{K}_{II} , \hat{K}_{III} , the phase angle ψ and the dimensionless energy release rate \hat{J} are defined by

$$\hat{K}_I + i\hat{K}_{II} = \frac{(K_I + iK_{II}) h^{1/2} b h^{3/2}}{P \ell}, \quad \hat{K}_{III} = \frac{K_{III} b h^{3/2}}{P \ell}, \quad \psi = \tan^{-1}(\hat{K}_{II}/\hat{K}_I), \quad \hat{J} = \frac{J b^2 h^2 E_2}{P^2 \ell^2 (1 - \nu_2^2)} \quad (21)$$

where E_2 is the Young's modulus of material 2, ν_2 is the Poisson's ratio of material 2, P is the load

TABLE 1 Results of the Example Problem

	Category of bimaterial	J	\hat{K}_I	\hat{K}_{II}	\hat{K}_{III}	ψ
Case (1)	isotropic	0.9886	0.671	0.734	0.0167	47.59°
Case (2)	orthotropic	1.022	0.319	0.300	0.0348	43.18°
Case (3)	anisotropic	1.021	0.320	0.299	0.0248	42.93°

of the beam, b is the half width of the beam, h is the height of the beam, ℓ is the distance from the load to the support (Fig. 2). Since the differences of the compliance elastic coefficient matrices s_1 and s_2 between the case (1) and case(2) are small, the results of case (1) and case (2) are found to be close. The distributions of the amplitude tangential stress $f(\theta)/|K|$ and the amplitude of tangential strain $g(\theta)/|K|$ in the case of isotropic bimaterial are shown in Fig. 4. It is found that there are two peaks respectively in material 1 and material 2. The two peaks of the two curves in Fig. 4 occur almost at the same positions. Thus, we may conclude that in the example there is no much difference between the two criteria in predicting the direction of crack branching.

In order to check the accuracy of our method, we consider the problem analyzed by Matos *et al.*⁴ The geometry and the boundary condition of the problem are the same as those of our example problem, but the two materials are isotropic. Initially, we use a coarse finite element mesh with 204 element and 226 nodes. Finally, a fine mesh is assigned the same as that of our example problem. The results are compared with those of Matos *et al.*⁴ as shown in Table 2. It is found that with increase in element number and node number, the results of \hat{J} , \hat{K}_I , \hat{K}_{II} and ψ approach those by Matos *et al.* based on 1120 eight-noded isoparametric elements and more than 4000 nodes. From Table 2, we conclude that the accuracy of this method is guaranteed if sufficiently large number of finite elements and nodal points is employed.

TABLE 2 Results of the Test Problem

	No. of Elements	No. of Nodes	\hat{J}		\hat{K}_I		\hat{K}_{II}		ψ		CPU time (sec)
			Values	Errors	Values	Errors	Values	Errors	Values	Errors	
Matos	1120	>4000	5.580	0.0%	0.700	0.0%	0.769	0.0%	47.70°	0.00%	
Case 1	204	226	4.243	-24.0%	0.578	-17.4%	0.643	-16.4%	48.03°	0.69%	113
Case 2	336	365	4.828	-13.5%	0.629	-10.1%	0.701	-8.8%	48.09°	0.82%	289
Case 3	480	529	5.240	-6.1%	0.668	-4.5%	0.718	-6.6%	47.06°	-1.34%	689
Case 4	640	689	5.303	-5.0%	0.671	-4.1%	0.734	-4.6%	47.59°	-0.23%	1371

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Allied-Signal Aerospace Company for the support of the research under grant number A-92-10-00007.

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